

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KOVACS****FIRST NAME: PAMELA****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: PROF. CLEENEWERCK**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical).
The author did use Zotero to insert references.
The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access) – *Is it possible to have access?*
The author used the following software: MSWord Office365 ProPlus.

A WELCOME REVIEW OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

After several years working in an international organization in a professional role that entails collaborating with authors from many different parts of the world, it was reassuring to review academic writing concepts as part of coursework for doctoral studies with EUCLID University. Colleagues from diverse backgrounds often think uniquely about writing, appropriate style, and use of language, which can lead to the need for patient exchange. Clarity of expectations is welcome. While many of the concepts presented in the *Euclid ACA Coursepack* for the first period of the course “International Academic Writing” have become internalized from previous studies, the thorough specifications provide an important reminder of the need for attention to detail and consistency.

In a professional setting, the precision required for strong writing is sometimes viewed as a luxury reserved for academics. The materials remind that strong research and writing *is* time consuming, requiring both creative and critical thinking (EUCLID 2015, 3); yet, there are also good habits that increase the likelihood of positive results.

Several themes introduced prompted deeper reflection as I reviewed the course materials. In this paper I will focus on one element (plagiarism) that I need to reinforce continuously in my own work with colleagues from different backgrounds, two elements (first person singular and plain language) that will be a distinct change for me, and one element (a “politically correct” reference) that emphasizes distinctions between American and British English, which, for a Canadian, too often meld.

2) **SELECT WRITING ELEMENTS**

a) Plagiarism

On many occasions I have found myself explaining to colleagues why work cannot simply be copied and pasted without attribution and why professional integrity dictates care and attention to avoid plagiarism. I appreciated the use of the term “unethical” as part of the description highlighting the importance of this topic (EUCLID 2015, 12). In a fast-paced world where information is ubiquitous online, taking the time to discern authorship, trace ideas, and ensure correct citations to original sources can seem removed from ethics; yet these actions speak to the core of professionalism, both in behavior and as reflected in writing. As presented by Euclid, plagiarism relates to academic honesty, but also to safeguarding the advancement of ideas that fuel academic progress.

The indication of why plagiarism extends to ideas and concepts and not just direct quotations is crucial, emphasizing correct use of paraphrasing as a tool to demonstrate understanding through restatement. If in doubt, I tend to encourage colleagues to use citations and it was thus helpful to reflect further on when not to cite. The example of common knowledge presents an interesting study (EUCLID 2015, 29-32).

Common knowledge can be seemingly easy to appreciate when understood as repetitive information from many different sources (EUCLID 2015, 31), yet on issues where there is significant disagreement or fundamentally opposed views, it is often necessary to delve deeper and consider the interests that might underlie certain stated facts or positions. While the presented example regarding smoking is appreciable in modern times as common knowledge given the accompanying level of scientific knowledge, in the recent past, such a statement may have prompted significant backlash. And even in modern times, common knowledge can be under fire. The attention and ethical care that accompanies academic writing is thus all the more important when framed as advancing knowledge and understanding about issues and topics that matter.

b) First Person Singular and Plain Language Usage

One writing technique that is often used professionally is to adopt a style other than first person singular, which is very personal. This will be a fundamental adjustment for me as I move forward with the Euclid program. Utilizing first person singular is uncommon in my professional role and would not represent “bad advice” from a teacher as described in the materials (EUCLID 2015, 44). This also holds true for “Latin Abbreviations and Expressions,” which are common and even encouraged in the legal profession (EUCLID 2015, 78-83). It is well-noted that plain language will be preferable for a wider audience, and, *inter alia*, this change will be welcome, as will use of first person singular. Indeed, these changes may be beneficial overall, forcing both clarity in word selection and stronger conviction in statement.

There can be anonymity and arms-length distance in not using the “I” pronoun. While it is understood that first person singular will not be accepted for major papers, reinforcing an academic style and rigor, for response papers, usage cultivates a more personal formulation. Utilizing first person singular facilitates a more open reflection, concretely drawing in the background and experience of the author. It is anticipated this will help me engage with content differently, through a combination of personal understanding and applied knowledge.

c) Political Correctness

Finally, one example presented in relation to political correctness and particularly differences between American and British English (EUCLID 2015, 54-59) provided a moment for reflection in relation to the importance of words and context for meaning.

In the province where I grew up, there is a town where the slogan appearing on the highway sign for many years was ‘the land of rape and honey.’ This referred to the prevalence of rapeseed (EUCLID 2015, 57) and honey production in the region. It was not until my teenage years that the sign attracted attention and, ultimately, renaming as a canola crop. Understandably, the term ‘rape’ outside a farming context carried a much different connotation and immediate understanding as years passed.

The selection of terms and how they will be received by different audiences is important, and can also signal the author’s background or bias. As a Canadian, these issues can be all the more challenging as, with a dominant American neighbor geographically but a British Commonwealth legacy, it is difficult to filter the influence of both styles of English. Canadians must often adopt one dialect or the other, while somehow not losing their own distinct “sociolectic value” (EUCLID 2015, 54).

3) CONCLUSION

I look forward to continuing coursework and applying a refreshed understanding of writing, both in a reflective and academic sense. I anticipate returning to the proffered short-hand reminders and checklists regarding important elements to keep in mind. Additionally, the Latin glossary and distinctions between American and British English can prove useful, both within the Euclid degree program and in my professional role, if not my personal role as a Canadian. My conversations with colleagues from around the world will be enhanced as we exchange on the core elements of strong writing. It is always beneficial to build knowledge and exposure beyond one’s own immediate familiarity.

REFERENCES

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